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D3.1 VITALISE Service Specification

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D3.1 VITALISE Service Specification

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D3.1 VITALISE Service Specification

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
LL	Living Lab
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ER	External Researchers
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier
API	Application Programming Interface
GUI	Graphical User Interface
DP	Discovery Portal
PC	Personal Computer
SDG	Synthetic Data Generation
SDV	Synthetic Data Vault
HR	Heart Rate
CSV	Comma Separated Values
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

Abstract

This deliverable reports on the VITALISE service specification. First, it describes the requirements (borrowed from D2.8) where the VITALISE data-sharing ICT solution is grounded. Next, it describes the architecture defined to support the targeted services, the different components that compose the VITALISE service architecture, their role and the technologies used to develop them. Following, the iterative prototyping approach is described, explaining the functionalities on each prototype version developed up to date, and describing the workflows implemented on each of them. Finally, conclusions on the current development status and planned next steps are reported.

Executive summary

This deliverable is of report nature as specified in the GA. The deliverable aims to present the VITALISE service specification and architecture related to the VITALISE information and communication technologies (ICT) tools that are being developed in WP3.

The main aim of the designed architecture is to manage the data on each Living Lab (LL) infrastructure and to share it based on the privacy, ethics and IPR legislation and policies established by each LL infrastructure. The main services provided by this architecture are:

- Common ICT infrastructure tools for LLs to upload, capture, and securely offer access to (controlled) data harmonized with the VITALISE data model.
- A portal for external researchers (ER) to explore metadata of data stored in LLs, request and check anonymous or synthetic data (Synthetic data is artificial data generated by a model trained or built to replicate real data based on its distributions (i.e., shape and variance) and structure (i.e., correlations among the attributes) (El Emam 2019)), schedule the remote execution of analyses, and register the results of the remotely executed analyses.
- A Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) cloud server to register and store the remotely executed analysis results and assign an immutable identifier to the performed experiment (author, time, script, dataset, and results).

The reported information in this deliverable mainly resulted from Task 3.1 (Service architecture definition, federated authentication, and Integration). However, this task is dependable on other tasks from the WP3:

- Task 2.4 (User requirements for ICT tools)
- Task 3.2 (Extensible VITALISE data model)
- Task 3.3 (Living Lab Infrastructure API and core communication modules)
- Task 3.4 (Anonymisation mechanism and Synthetic data engine toolkit development)
- Task 3.5 (RAI Cloud Server)
- Task 3.6 (RAI Certified Node dataset curation, preservation, and provision of access for Living Lab access)
- Task 3.8 (VITALISE Portal for data discovery and federated data access)

From a technical perspective, the architecture has been designed and implemented using the Python and NodeJS programming frameworks, containerisation (Docker) technologies with docker-compose deployment technologies, JSON text data format, and an application programming interfaces (API) (see section 2.4 for more technical implementation details).

The actual deliverable presents the current design of the VITALISE service architecture and some explanations of its actual developments (prototypes v0 and v1). Future prototype developments are planned with the specified and not implemented functionalities. Despite the architecture design might be modified if needed according to the defined specifications in the GA, no significant changes regarding the general architecture are anticipated. Relevant content of this document will be updated if deemed necessary, but initially, it is not planned.

Note: Document does not include confidential information under intellectual property (IP) analysis. Complete deliverable will be released upon finalisation of the IP analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable is of report nature as specified in the GA. The aim is to present the VITALISE service specification and architecture to manage the data on each LL infrastructure and to share it based on the privacy, ethics and IPR legislation and policies established by each LL infrastructure. The document presents and describes the VITALISE service architecture, composed of the VITALISE ICT tools developed by different Tasks of WP3. Additionally, some descriptions of the architecture's actual development status (prototype V0 and prototype 1) and future developments are provided.

1.2 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** provides information regarding the purpose of the document and its structure.
- **Section 2** presents and describes the VITALISE service and its user and technical requirements.
- **Section 3** describes the architecture of the VITALISE service and the interactions between the different modules that compose the service.
- **Section 4** explains the actual developments of the architecture and the ideas for future developments.
- **Section 5** provides some concluding remarks for this deliverable.

2 VITALISE service overview

The VITALISE service architecture has been designed to comply with the required ICT tools for the harmonization, standardization and public usage of data stored in different LLs. Apart from that, this architecture also offers tools to ER to advance in data analysis tasks using the data generated and stored in different LLs securely and privately. This section presents the VITALISE service, the user stories, and the technical requirements.

2.1 Description of the VITALISE service

VITALISE proposes to provide open access to LLs captured data for processing, enabling an open, fair, and reliable access to the research community where every researcher will be accredited for their work and all research data will be equally accessible for processing without violating data protection regulations. In this sense, the VITALISE service will support ICT tools for research and data analysis services.

2.2 Modules of the VITALISE service

The VITALISE service has been divided into four main modules (Data Model, Discovery Portal, RAI Node and RAI Cloud Server) to facilitate the scalability and deployment of the service. Each module is specialized in different tasks and communicates with the other ones. Next, each module is described, specifying its objectives.

Data Model

The standardized and harmonized VITALISE Data Model aims to harmonize all data generated from the different LLs under a universal data format. The Data Model transforms data from different sources into the defined data format. All data that resides in the systems must follow this defined data model.

Discovery Portal (DP)

The DP, which is presented as a web-based GUI, is the common entry point for the different VITALISE ICT tools and ER. ER can use the DP to perform the following operations:

1. Explore, identify, and query the LL available research data.
2. Interact with the RAI Node for (1) getting a synthetic version of the data, (2) remotely testing locally developed algorithms with real data and (3) registering results.

RAI Node

The RAI Node is the software package that will be installed in each LL. This software package is responsible for the following tasks:

1. Collect, prepare, and transform data gathered for each LL into the harmonized VITALISE data model.
2. Inform and update the DP on new data available for research.
3. Generate synthetic and shareable data representing real data generated from each LL to allow researchers to develop algorithms locally on their PCs.
4. Execute ER developed algorithms with the real data stored internally in each LL.
5. Request scientific results registration upon ER request (through the DP).

RAI Cloud Server

The RAI Cloud Server is a registration service to store all information regarding remotely executed analyses.

2.3 User stories

This subsection contains the user stories that have guided the technical requirements definition and the design of the VITALISE service. These user requirements have been defined and compiled in

the D2.8 (First version of user requirements) after some workshops and dissemination activities developed within Task 2.4 (User requirements for ICT tools) and internal discussions between technical partners.

2.3.1 User roles

Between the previously described modules of the VITALISE service, the RAI Node and the DP are the ones that require user interactions. Only specific personnel will interact with the RAI Node since it will be installed in each LL and the DP is the main module that will allow ER to interact with the system. The other two modules (Data Model and RAI Cloud Server) do not require user interactions because they operate in the background.

Four distinct user roles have been identified considering the user interactions intended with the VITALISE service. Next, each defined user role is explained:

- **Controller:** the “owner” of the datasets uploaded from a LL or the manager of the RAI Node installed in a LL. The users that can take these types of actions can be (1) LL or data manager, (2) project or pilot manager, (3) panel manager, (4) business developer of the LL or (5) information specialist or librarian. These kinds of users will always perform their actions through the RAI Node.
- **Processor:** individuals or organizations that wish to gain access to the service and process the uploaded data throughout the DP. Users who can take this role are ER and teachers who may use the service for educational purposes. They will execute their actions only through the DP interacting with the rest of the modules through background operations.
- **Administrator:** technical partner(s) responsible for the operation and maintenance of the system. They can interact with all modules of the service.
- **Public:** individuals that have no active role in the processing of datasets (journal editors or members of the public). These users can only perform their limited actions through the DP.

2.3.2 Actions per role

All actions the different users can perform according to their role have been grouped into three distinct categories and subsequently allocated to sub-categories. The categorization has been as follows:

1. Datasets: upload, explore, synthetic data and others.
2. Analysis: upload script, run scripts, get results, resolve RAI identifier and others.
3. Forum: submit a request, identify potential partners and submit a complaint.

Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 describe the actions each role can perform when using the VITALISE service.

Table 1: Controller actions

Category		As a controller, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upload datasets. 2. Set the availability/visibility of all datasets I have uploaded. 3. Provide access to other researchers to upload their datasets 4. Manage the metadata of the datasets I have uploaded. 5. Include the study protocol in the metadata of the datasets I have uploaded. 6. Describe the level of privacy of the data included in the uploaded dataset (if they are fully anonymized or not).
	Explore	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. View all datasets in the network (look for dataset statistics, topics, which are mostly used, and which instruments/sensors are mostly used). 8. View/Access statistics on dataset visibility, dataset usage and produced from the RAI server/node.

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	Synthetic data	9. Show the privacy metrics and confirm the metrics that are over the threshold of the synthetic data I have generated.
	Other	10. Install the RAI node in a local computer through easy steps. 11. Mark a data structure and format officially accepted in the harmonization process.
Analysis	Upload script	12. View and check the scripts uploaded by researchers for the analysis of datasets I have uploaded. 13. Initiate the automated flagging for malicious scripts.
	Run script	14. Approve the scripts and analysis of researchers on datasets I have uploaded. 15. Launch the analysis a researcher has requested to perform on datasets I have uploaded.
	Get results	16. Access/View statistics about the analysis done in datasets I have uploaded.
	Resolve RAI Identifier	17. Verify RAI identifiers.
	Other	18. Ensure that the analysis results maintain data security before allowing the resolution of the RAI Identifier.
Forum	Submit request	19. Receive notification and access/view categorized requests for datasets.
	Identify potential partners	<i>No action considered.</i>
	Submit complaint	20. Receive notifications and access/view complaints regarding data models, their extensions and possible changes that can be applied to them.

Table 2: Processor actions

Category		As a processor, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	1. Become a controller, i.e., upload my own datasets on a RAI Node.
	Explore	2. Search available datasets and view <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. background information on data collection procedures of the dataset, b. what studies have been published based on the datasets, c. other results of the analysis performed on a dataset, as well as requests for the synthetic data of the dataset, d. usage statistics of the datasets, e. descriptive statistics of the datasets, f. licensing or possible restrictions when using the datasets. 3. Search for available datasets based on topics, country of origin, organization, users etc.
	Synthetic data	4. Request synthetic data for a specific dataset. 5. Receive synthetic data for a specific dataset. 6. View metrics related to the quality of the synthetic data. 7. Choose the synthetic data format type (CSV, JSON, etc.).
	Other	8. Have access to both quantitative and qualitative data. 9. Rate a dataset. 10. See user rating of a dataset. 11. Share a link to a dataset.
Analysis	Upload script	12. Choose a dataset of interest and upload a script file to perform my preferred analysis.

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	Run script	13. Develop and run locally script on synthetic data before initiating the actual analysis. 14. Have the option to run a script on multiple datasets from the same RAI node. 15. Receive feedback on the running time of my analysis.
	Get results	16. View the results of my analysis. 17. Download my results in my chosen format (SPV, CSV, JSON, etc.).
	Resolve RAI Identifier	18. Resolve RAI identifiers for the authentication of my analysis.
	Other	19. Share a link to the results of my analysis. 20. View publications based on my analysis.
Forum	Submit request	21. Access the forum and submit a request for a specific dataset. 22. Request clarifications on a dataset's variables, metadata, etc.
	Identify potential partners	23. View affiliations of the controller and other processors at a person/organization level.
	Submit complaint	24. Access the forum and submit a complaint about a specific dataset or other issues.

Table 3: Administrator actions

Category		As an administrator, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	1. Add and remove users.
	Search/View	2. Govern the approval process for a processor to gain access to a dataset.
	Synthetic data	<i>No action considered.</i>
	Other	3. Grant access rights to controllers.
Analysis	<i>Not applicable.</i>	
Forum	Submit request	<i>No action considered.</i>
	Identify potential partners	<i>No action considered.</i>
	Submit complaint	4. Evaluate complaints. 5. Update data models based on complaints.

Table 4: Public user actions

Category		As a public user, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	<i>Not applicable.</i>
	Search/View	
	Synthetic data	
	Other	1. View publications that have used one or more datasets.
Analysis	Upload script	<i>Not applicable.</i>
	Run script	
	Get results	
	Resolve RAI Identifier	2. Verify the analysis and its results.
	Other	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet.</i>
Forum	<i>Not applicable.</i>	

2.4 Technical requirements

The technical requirements to fulfil the VITALISE service have been defined considering the user stories presented in the above subsection. Different requirements have been defined for each module, and the technologies used to fulfil them have been selected. In the next lines, the requirements, and selected technologies for each module of the VITALISE service are gathered.

2.4.1 Data Model

The only requirement for the VITALISE Data Model is to have a data format schema to define the standardized data model to harmonize data generated from LLs. The JSON data format has been used, using JSON Schema (JsonSchema 2022) to define the data model.

2.4.2 Discovery Portal

For the development of the VITALISE Discovery Portal (VDP), multiple technologies have been used in order to facilitate the development of a fully operational, efficient and scalable web application that offers an interconnected broker system, enabling access to VITALISE's LL data operations. The technical requirements and the selected technologies for this module are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Requirements and technologies of the VITALISE Discovery Portal

Requirement	Objective	Technology
A web application that can handle front-end flexibility and efficient communication with other VITALISE Components.	Use a runtime environment and frameworks that permit communication with VITALISE components via APIs and offers scalable performance.	Node JS (Node.js 2022) and Express JS (Express.js 2022a)
Non-relational database system. Alignment with RAI Node and Data model data storing requirements.	Store Metadata in JSON format. Store specific ids based on communications to facilitate exchange of information via the APIs.	MongoDB (MongoDB 2022c) and Mongoose (Mongoose 2022d)
Responsive, user friendly and visually appealing web application.	Enhance VDP with components and customizations that make access and actions easy to understand and the app more friendly to the user.	Bootstrap (Bootstrap 2022)
Server-Client communication.	Enables real-time, bi-directional communication between web clients and servers.	Socket.IO (Socket.IO 2022e)
Containerisation of software.	Uses Docker Engine to host VDP containers and Docker Compose for deployment purposes.	Docker (Docker 2022b)
Only authorized users can use the VDP. Alignment with VITALISE authentication methods.	User's access to the VDP is enabled via basic auth credentials (username, password). All API calls to the VDP use the same authentication.	Basic access authentication

2.4.3 RAI Node

The RAI Node of the VITALISE service has been developed in the Python programming language and using containerisation (Docker) technologies with docker-compose deployment technologies for deploying the RAI Nodes in the LLs. Table 5 gathers the requirements of the RAI Node and the technologies used to fulfil each of them.

Table 6: Requirements and technologies of the VITALISE RAI Node

Requirement	Objective	Technology
A web framework for building an API in the Python programming language.	Provide endpoints for LL managers and ER to interact with the service.	FastAPI (FastAPI 2022)
Non-relational database system.	Store data generated from LLs.	MongoDB (MongoDB 2022c)
A JSON schema validator	Validate that the transformed data follow the defined data schema.	jsonschema python package (JsonSchema 2022)
Synthetic Data Generation (SDG) approaches and tools	Generate a synthetic version of the real data that is stored in LLs.	SDV python package (SDV 2022)
A file storage server	Save the remotely executed analysis results and the generated synthetic data.	MinIO (MinIO 2022)
A task queue system	Queue the tasks that the RAI Node must process (SDG, remote execution of analysis, etc).	Celery (Celery 2022) and RabbitMQ (RabbitMQ 2022)

2.4.4 RAI Cloud Server

The RAI Cloud service module has been developed in NodeJS using a web-framework to implement a REST API for other module interaction for experiment registration. Additionally, it features a non-relational database and a message broker. Table 7 gathers the requirements of the RAI Node and the technologies used to fulfil each of them.

Table 7: Requirements and technologies of the RAI Cloud Server

Requirement	Objective	Technology
Web Framework	Provide a REST API interface for other service interaction with the module.	HAPIJS (NodeJS package)
Message Broker	Allow requests to be queued and elaborated when possible. Allow failed requests to be re-elaborated later in time.	RabbitMQ
Non-Relational Database	Database storage service to archive requests data and logs.	MongoDB (MongoDB 2022c)

3 VITALISE service architecture

This section will provide descriptions of the overall VITALISE service architecture and all the modules that compose the service (Data model, discovery portal, RAI node and RAI cloud server).

3.1 Overall VITALISE service architecture

The designed architecture for the VITALISE service is depicted in Figure 1. There it can be seen the modules of the service and how they are connected. Of the four modules, three of them (Discovery Portal, RAI Node and RAI Cloud Server) have been independently designed and developed, while the Data Model module is used in both the Discovery Portal and the RAI Node. Regarding authentication, there is an overarching federated authentication mechanism that goes over the depicted service architecture diagram. Despite a single RAI Node is depicted in the diagram, the architecture support multiple RAI Nodes and it's desirable to have at least a RAI Node per each data-managing and sharing service provider (one per each Living Lab with required resource and trained personnel).

Figure 1: VITALISE service architecture

As explained in the previous section, the Discovery Portal is the common entry point for processors to communicate with the other modules and ICT tools of the VITALISE service. Thus, this module communicates with the RAI Node and the RAI Cloud Server through their internal APIs. It provides the data catalogue of the data that resides in the LLs in compliance with the Data Model, the status tracking of tasks sent to the RAI Node and the option to public messages in the VITALISE forum service.

The RAI Node is installed in a controlled way in each LL using federated authentication to provide and execute the tasks regarding the data storing, queries and requests, the remote execution of analyses and the registration of results. All these tasks are requested and scheduled by processors through the Discovery Portal. Thus, this module receives requests from the DP to execute them in a controlled environment and sends notifications to the Discovery Portal for the status tracking of the tasks. It also uses the inner API and the API of the RAI Cloud Server to handle the requests that arrive to the RAI Node regarding the registration of results. The RAI Node is also the entry point for controllers to register their LL and upload data to the incorporated controlled database.

The RAI Cloud Server is the registration service to store all information regarding the locally and remotely executed analyses. This way, processors can make requests using the Discovery Portal to query all registered RAI and find information about them.

In the next subsections, each module is explained from a technical and architectural perspective to better understand each and how it works. First, the Data Model is explained, then the Discovery Portal, next the RAI Node and finally, the RAI Cloud Server.

3.2 Data Model

The VITALISE Data Model presents an extensible, robust, and reused data reference model to guarantee that the model described is well suited for the VITALISE service architecture and database and data querying. Following the VITALISE modeling and implementation requirements, which were defined in collaboration with the LL partners, the VITALISE Data Model is based on the OmH Standard (OpenmHealth 2022). The sensor resource description recommendations provided in this standard have been taken as a starting point, where common schemas define the meaningful distinctions for each clinical measure, increasing the overall clinical utility of digital health data.

Subsequently, the schemas interested in VITALISE LL into a unique and novel data model have been integrated. This is fully related to the LL modeling requirements and can also be used from external LL. Since some of the recommended devices/measurements could not be mapped to the OmH, other health standards have been used, such as the Web Things (Webthings 2022), Open Connectivity Foundation (OCF 2022) and Schema (Schema.org 2022), where new JSON schemas were designed based on the proposed properties and relationships. Specifically, a reference and extensible data model has been designed. This data model can:

- Represent information made available via the ICT tools (i.e., BMI, heart rate, age, sex).
- Provide further information and metadata like descriptive statistics, which can enrich the existing data elements (i.e., mean, mode).
- Provide personal info for the users (patient's id)
- Ensure harmonization of the information exchanged between the individual VITALISE service modules.
- Achieve that the provided data model can be further extended with domain knowledge pertinent to the VITALISE use cases.

Apart from that, a Data Point model has been constructed. This Data Point model represents the clinical measurements and fully aligns with the LL requirements specified by Petsani et al. (Petsani et al. 2022). In addition, the Dataset model has also been defined, where user's info (for clinical applications or non-ill /wellbeing purposes) and metadata are provided, respectively. All these three models have been designed based on the project Requirements & Considering privacy compliant with the GDPR data protection regulation (Radley-Gardner, Beale, and Zimmermann 2016). The Data Model is accessible in the Gitlab team of the VITALISE project (<https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model>).

3.3 Discovery portal

The VITALISE Discovery Portal (VDP) refers to the development of a fully operational, efficient and scalable web application that offers an interconnected system, enabling access to VITALISE's LL data operations. The architectural concept and innovation behind the VDP are that it acts as a broker between the Processor user (client) and the RAI Nodes (server), mimicking the Service Oriented Architecture but instead of "Service Discovery", in the VDP approach, "Data Discovery" is enabled instead.

Figure 2: VDP Concept.

The VDP offers a user-friendly web interface to Processor users in order to enable the initiation of procedures available in the VITALISE ICT tools stack. The VITALISE functions available via the VDP include the following:

- **Data Discovery:** The user has access to the metadata of LL datasets via the VDP. A search bar and filters can be used in order to search through datasets according to the user's needs. The dataset's overview information (e.g., title, description, RAI Node host) is presented and each dataset can be visited in a separate view for further information. Further information includes metadata details as well as descriptive statistics and visualizations for the respective dataset.
- **Request Synthetic Data Generation:** Following the observation of the metadata of each dataset, the user may request the generation of synthetic data via the VDP User Interface (UI), by selecting one or more datasets. The VDP API (Application Programming Interface) requests synthetic data and offers the results for the user to download from the VDP UI.
- **Run Experiment:** The user may initiate an Experiment Run via the VDP UI by providing the three required files;
 - o Experiment .py file
 - o Experiment Configuration .yaml file
 - o Requirements .txt file

When the files are submitted, the VDP API will ask for the remote execution of the experiment and the results can then be downloaded via the VDP UI.

- **RAI Node Registration:** There is, additionally, the possibility for admin users to register a RAI Node by providing a RAI Node ID and a RAI Node URL.

The VDP, in alignment with the rest of VITALISE ICT systems, currently it uses basic authentication (federated authentication and session based JWT web tokens usage is planned and under development, see section 3.6) in order to secure the system from unwanted access. The user is provided with universal credentials (username, password) in order to enter the VDP and all API calls to the VDP must be accompanied by the same authentication credentials (session based JWT web tokens usage is planned and under development). The user must additionally sign-up and subsequently login to the VDP in order to access its functions.

The above-mentioned methods including the user-friendly UI, the API communications and the authentication strategies form an end-to-end system and a complete functional solution for the Processor user, facilitating access to metadata and LL datasets and to various functions and procedures that are offered in the VITALISE ICT tools WP (WP3).

3.4 RAI Node

The RAI Node is the software package that is responsible for (1) storing data generated from LLs, (2) providing SD and anonymized data to processors, (3) executing analyses remotely with the real data stored internally in the module, and (4) requesting results registration. This module, which will be installed in each LL, has been developed following a microservice architecture design composed of six services that communicate with each other in the way depicted in Figure 3. These different services are bundled through containerisation (Docker) technologies and managed through docker-

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compose container orchestration technology. The selection of these technologies facilitates the deployment and update of the RAI Nodes in different LLs.

Figure 3: Architecture of the VITALISE RAI Node. Inspired from (Hernandez et al. 2022)

In the next lines, each service and how they communicate with each other is described:

- **MongoDB** is a distributed NoSQL database system (MongoDB 2022c) used in the RAI Node to store the data securely generated in the different LLs.
- **RabbitMQ** is an open-source message broker (RabbitMQ 2022) used in the RAI Node to communicate the services of the module and queue tasks. Specifically, this broker is used to queue and schedule SDG tasks and remote execution of analyses.
- The **MinIO Server** is an object storage server (MinIO 2022) used in the RAI Node to store: (1) the trained SDG models, (2) the generated SD in both CSV and JSON data formats, (3) the real data that has been used for SDG in both CSV and JSON data formats, (4) the necessary files for the remote execution of the experiments with real data stored in MongoDB, and (5) the results produced as part of the remote execution of experiments with the real data stored in MongoDB.
- The **RAI Hub** is an API developed in the Python programming language using the FastAPI framework (FastAPI 2022) that handles the requests from users with the controller role (directly) and users with the processor role (through the DP). It also works as an intermediary between the SD Generator and Remote Execution System of the RAI Node. Thereby, it has access to RabbitMQ (to queue tasks for the other modules), MongoDB (to store and query available data in the RAI Node), and the MinIO Server (to retrieve generated SD in CSV and JSON data formats and to write input files for the remote execution of experiments with the available data in MongoDB). The code for this module is available in the Gitlab group of the VITALISE project (<https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta>).
- The **SD Generator** is an MQTT client subscribed to the SD topic of RabbitMQ and developed in the Python programming language. This module is responsible for training SDG models and generating SD. Thus, it has access to RabbitMQ (to subscribe to the SD topic), MongoDB (to query available data in the RAI Node according to the specified query parameters), and the MinIO server (to store the trained SDG models and the generated SD in both CSV and

JSON data formats). The code for this component is available in the Gitlab group of the VITALISE project (<https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/synth>).

- The **Remote Execution System** is a distributed system developed using Celery (Celery 2022) and the Python programming language. This service processes and queues the tasks regarding the remote execution of analyses with data stored in MongoDB that are sent through RabbitMQ by the RAI Node. It has access to RabbitMQ (to see the queued tasks regarding the remote execution), MongoDB (to query available RD), and the MinIO server (to access the necessary files for the remote execution of each experiment and to store the results of them). The code for this component is available in the Gitlab group of the VITALISE project (<https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/bayaz>).

3.5 RAI cloud server

The RAI Cloud Server is the VITALISE application module responsible for accepting data registration.

Note: Document does not include confidential information under intellectual property (IP) analysis. Complete deliverable will be released upon finalisation of the IP analysis.

3.6 Federated authentication

For all the VITALISE Platform components that require a User Authentication process, the Federated authentication module serves as a standard "Authentication Server." On top of the VITALISE components, it serves as a Single Sign On (SSO) server, which performs the function of a firewall. Keycloak is used for this implementation¹, which is a tool that supports the following standard protocols: OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0, and SAM.

Figure 4: Architecture of the Federated authentication module

When users access any VITALISE component that needs authentication, they are redirected to keycloak. After the redirect, the login process is done by keycloak, by verifying the user's credentials which are stored in a database using PostgreSQL. For each user, PostgreSQL contains one field for the username and the one for a one-way hashed password; the password is one-way hashed to

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org>

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enhance security. If the login is successful, keycloak generates an authenticated session and provides a session id and a Json Web Token (JWT) that contains encoded information about the user and the user is redirected back to the initially referred URL. When a VITALISE component does a remote API call to another VITALISE component, the latter component validates through keycloak the previously generated token in order to allow the remote API call. In Figure 4, an instance of a former VITALISE component is the Discovery Portal while and the latter VITALISE component is the RAI node.

4 Prototypes development

Current developments of the prototypes for the VITALISE service will be explained in this section. From the start of the project until the date the manuscript was written, two prototypes have been fully developed and tested: prototype V0 and prototype V1. Each of these is explained in the next subsections, and the final subsection will present the functionalities intended to add to future prototypes.

4.1 Prototype V0

In prototype V0 of the VITALISE service, the most basic actions for controllers and processors were implemented. Due to the lack of data sources format from the LLs, this prototype is only compatible with heart rate (HR) data generated from Fitbit sources. Apart from that, even though one RAI Node will be installed in each LL, for simplification, only one RAI Node has been deployed. Furthermore, the SDG models from the SDV python package² and the data in CSV format have been used in this prototype for the SDG requests. In this prototype, the following actions can be performed:

- A controller or LL manager can submit HR generated from Fitbit sources to the RAI node of the LL.
- A processor (for example, an ER) can query the number of HR entries, request SD of HR data available in the RAI Node, execute analysis locally, schedule them remotely, and register the analysis results.

Regarding the security and authentication mechanisms implemented in this prototype, HTTPS has been used to have secure communications through the network, and HTTP basic access authentication method has been implemented with username and password to authorise the REST API calls between the Discovery Portal, the RAI Nodes, and the RAI Cloud Server. Authentication credentials were shared in advance.

In this section, the workflows of the prototype V0 for each of the presented actions are illustrated and described in detail.

4.1.1 Upload data from Living Labs

Figure 5 shows the workflow of the VITALISE service that will be executed when a controller wants to upload HR data to the RAI Node of the LL.

Figure 5: Prototype V0 workflow for data uploading

Every time a controller uploads new HR data from a Fitbit device, the RAI Hub of the RAI Node transforms it to the VITALISE Data Model format, and the SD generator trains the SDG model to generate SD later when a processor requests it. Finally, the controller is notified of the results of the request. If an exception occurs (internal connection error, transformation error, input source format error, etc.), the controller is notified of the exception error, and the request should be done again.

² <https://sdv.dev/>

Apart from that, the descriptive statistics of all HR data available in the RAI Node are computed and sent to the DP to update the metadata of the available data in the LLs.

4.1.2 Explore data and request synthetic data

Figure 6 shows the workflow for data querying and SDG. Anytime, users with the processor role (ER or teachers) can query the number of HR entries through the DP. After that, they can request the generation of SD of the available HR values (without filtering or querying them).

Figure 6: Prototype V0 workflow for data exploring and synthetic data request

When the SDG request arrives at the RAI Node through the DP, the following steps are executed:

1. The RAI Hub generates the `sd_request_id` (unique identifier of the SD request), and the `hash_query_real` (unique identifier of the real data that has been used for SDG) hardcoded and fixed to “*heart_rate*” in this prototype.
2. The SD generator generates SD using the previously trained SDG model (when a controller uploads HR data to the RAI Node).
3. The DP is notified that SD is ready, and the processor is notified with the provision of an URL to download the data.

When the processor requesting the SD uses the generated URL, the SD is downloaded in CSV format. A zip file is downloaded with two files: (1) the info file that contains metadata of the SD (`sd_request_id`, `hash_query_real`, timestamp and description) and the data file that contains the requested SD. More information about the SDG workflow of this prototype can be found in the publication by Hernandez et al. (Hernandez et al. 2022).

4.1.3 Execute analysis locally and remotely

After requesting and obtaining SD of HR values, processors can develop local algorithms using this data. Then, they can request the remote execution of those with the real values of HR that reside inside the RAI Node. Figure 7 shows the workflow for this action.

When a controller uses the DP to request the remote execution of an experiment, the request is sent to the RAI Node. Once the RAI Node receives this request, the execution of this experiment is scheduled and queued to the Remote execution schedule. Then, the Remote execution scheduler runs the experiment with the real values of HR inside the RAI Node, and when the results are ready, they are saved in the MinIO server, and the processor is notified through the DP.

After receiving this notification, the processor can request the analysis results through the DP. When the RAI Node receives this request, the RAI Hub finds these results in the MinIO server and is sent

to the processor through the DP. This workflow can be repeated until the processor is happy with the results.

Figure 7: Prototype V0 workflow for executing analyses locally and remotely

4.1.4 Register analysis results

The last workflow implemented in this prototype is the registration results. Once the processor that requested the remote execution of an analysis is happy with the obtained results, they can register them in the RAI Cloud server. The executed workflow in this action is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Prototype V0 workflow for registering analyses results

When a controller uses the DP to request the registration of the results obtained when executing the analysis remotely, the request is sent to the RAI Node. Once the RAI Node receives this request, another request is sent to the RAI Cloud Server to register the results.

4.2 Prototype V1

In prototype V1 of the VITALISE service, the actions for controllers and processors implemented in prototype V0 have been improved, and some new actions have been added. As in the previous prototype, due to the lack of data sources format from the LLs, this prototype is only compatible with heart rate (HR) and steps data generated from Fitbit sources. Apart from that, even though one RAI Node will be installed in each LL, for simplification, two RAI Nodes have been deployed in different locations (VICOM and AUTH). In this prototype, the following actions have been added in addition to those provided by prototype V0:

- A controller can register the RAI Node in the DP and new datasets and people (with their corresponding metadata) in their RAI Node.

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- A controller can upload an anonymized datapoint of HR or steps values previously transformed to the VITALISE Data Model.
- A processor can query the metadata of each registered dataset in all RAI Nodes to request SD or anonymized data according to the defined query parameters.

Regarding the security and authentication mechanisms, the same implementation as in prototype V0 has been kept in prototype V1. HTTPS has been used to have secure communications through the network, and HTTP basic access authentication method has been implemented with username and password to authorise the REST API calls between the Discovery Portal, the RAI Nodes, and the RAI Cloud Server. Authentication credentials were shared in advance. In following prototypes, the approach for authentication and authorization described in section 3.6, will be implemented.

In this section, the workflows of the prototype V1 for each of the presented actions are illustrated and described in detail.

4.2.1 Submit data from Living Labs

In this prototype, the first time a controller wants to submit data generated in the LL to the RAI Node, they must register the RAI Node in the DP. The controller does this registration through the DP, as shown in Figure 9. Moreover, in this prototype, the HR and steps data that are available to submit must be joined to a dataset and can also represent the data of a person. For this reason, the option to register datasets and persons in the RAI Node has been implemented. Alternatively, a controller can transform the source HR or steps data point into the VITALISE Data Model and submit it to the RAI Node through the RAI Hub. The complete workflow for these actions can be seen in Figure 9, and the descriptions are provided in the next lines.

Figure 9: Prototype V1 workflow for uploading data from LLs

Register dataset and person

When a controller requests the registration of a dataset or a person through the RAI Node with the required metadata for each type (shown in Table 8 for a dataset and Table 9 for a person), the RAI Hub generates the unique identifier (UUID) of the dataset or person and stores the dataset or person data in MongoDB, then, the generated UUID is returned to the controller to make them now which UUID represents the registered dataset or person.

Table 8: Metadata of a registered dataset

Parameter	Type	Description
name	string	Name of the dataset or study.
description	string	Description of the dataset or study.
author	string	Author of the dataset or study (individual or company).
anonymized	boolean	Represents if the data that will be joined to this dataset is anonymized (true) or not (false).

Table 9: Metadata of a registered person

Parameter	Type	Description
gender	categorical (Male/Female)	The gender of the person to be registered.
date_birth	date (YYYY-MM-DD)	The birthdate of the person to be registered.

Submit HR and steps data from the Fitbit source format

In this prototype, when a controller wants to upload HR or steps data from Fitbit devices to the RAI Node, they must specify to which dataset and person corresponds the data to be submitted, introducing the UUID of both the dataset and the person (the identifiers that are returned to the controller when they register a dataset or a person).

The workflow for uploading HR and steps data from Fitbit devices to the RAI Node is the same as in prototype 0 with few variations. Every time a controller uploads new data, the RAI Hub of the RAI Node transforms it to the VITALISE Data Model format and the transformed data is validated with a JSON Schema validator. Then, if the dataset corresponding to the uploaded data is not anonymized, the SD generator trains the SDG model to generate SD later when a processor requests it; otherwise, a new SDG model is not trained. Finally, the controller is notified of the results of the request. If an exception occurs (internal connection error, transformation error, input source format error, etc.), it is notified of the exception error, and the request should be done again. Apart from that, the descriptive statistics of all HR and steps data available in the RAI Node are computed for each registered dataset and sent to the DP to update the metadata of the available data in the LLs.

Submit previously transformed HR and steps data

One of the new functionalities incorporated in the prototype V1 is the option for a controller to submit a previously transformed data point (for the moment, HR or steps) in compliance with the VITALISE Data Model and join to a dataset and person using the corresponding dataset and person UUIDs as parameters. In the workflow for this action, when a controller submits a previously transformed data point to the RAI Node, the RAI Hub validates it with a JSON Schema validator.

On the one hand, if the data point is validated, the submitted data point is compliant with the VITALISE Data Model. In this case, the data point is stored in MongoDB, and like in the other workflow, if the dataset corresponding to the uploaded data point is not anonymized, the SD generator trains the SDG model; otherwise, a new SDG model is not trained. Finally, the descriptive

statistics of all HR and steps data available in the RAI Node are computed for each registered dataset and sent to the DP to update the metadata of the available data in the LLs.

On the other hand, if there has been an error validating the data point, it is not compliant with the VITALISE Data Model. In this case, the controller is notified of this issue and the number of errors in the previously transformed data point. Then, the controller must fix the errors of the data point to make it compliant with the Data Model and try this request again.

Such as in the other workflows for submitting LLs data, if any exception occurs (internal connection error, transformation error, input source format error, etc.) during the workflow, the controller is notified of the exception error, and the request should be done again.

4.2.2 Explore data and request anonymized or synthetic data

The workflow for data querying and requesting SD or anonymized data for this prototype is quite different from prototype V0. Anytime, users with the processor role can query and visualize some descriptive statistics of the HR and steps values for each RAI Node and registered dataset through the DP. After that, they can query the available HR and steps values and request the generation of SD or anonymized data of the results of the applied query through the DP. The complete workflow for these actions is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Prototype V1 workflow for requesting synthetic or anonymized data

For requesting both SD and anonymized data, users with processor roles can query the available HR and steps data in the RAI Nodes by the parameters that are listed next:

- **datasets (required):** a list of the datasets UUIDs for querying the data. At least one valid dataset UUID is required.
- **gender:** gender of the subjects of interest (Male, Female or Both). All genders will be considered by default if none of them is selected.
- **birthdate_bigger_than:** the minimum birthdate of the subjects to query the data. If none is specified, no minimum birthdate will be applied.
- **birthdate_smaller_than:** the maximum birthdate of the subjects to query the data. If none is specified, no maximum birthdate will be applied.
- **model_nodes:** a list of the data nodes of interest (heart_rate and steps in this prototype). At least one node is required. If more than one is requested, all of them will be queried.

With these parameters, processors can request SD or anonymized data for the results of the requested query. It must be mentioned that due to technical issues, in this prototype, the query parameters are not considered for the generation of SD. This functionality is being implemented for future prototypes. Next, the workflows for SD and anonymized data requests are independently explained.

Synthetic Data request workflow

As in prototype V0, in this prototype, when a processor requests the generation of SD for a specified data query (only for datasets that are not anonymized), the request is sent to the RAI Node that contains the requested data. Inside this module, the following steps are executed:

1. The RAI Hub generates the *sd_request_id*, a unique identifier of the SD request in UUID format.
2. The RAI Hub filters the data according to the previously defined query parameters, generates the *hash_query_real* (unique identifier of the filtered or queried real data in UUID format), and stores a copy of the filtered data in the MinIO server.
3. The SD Generator generates SD using the previously trained SDG model. Since a generic SDG model is used, the generated SD comes from all values of each *model_node*. Thus, SDG is not query-specific in this prototype.
4. The SD Generator generates the info file that contains metadata of the SD request (*sd_request_id*, *hash_query_real*, timestamp and description) and saves the generated SD in the MinIO server in both JSON and CSV data formats together with this info file.
5. The DP is notified that SD is ready, and the processor is notified with the provision of an URL to download the SD through the DP.

When the processor requesting the SD uses the generated URL, the SD is downloaded in the requested format (JSON or CSV) from the MinIO server of the RAI Node. In this step, the processor obtains a zip file with some files: the info file that contains metadata of the SD (in JSON format) and one data file for each queried *model_node* that contains the requested SD of each model node in the requested format.

Anonymized Data request workflow

Additionally, when a processor requests anonymized data for a specified data query (only for anonymized datasets), the request is also sent to the RAI Node containing the requested data, in which similar steps that when requesting SD are executed:

1. The RAI Hub generates the *ad_request_id*, a unique identifier of the anonymized data request in UUID format.
2. The RAI Hub filters the data according to the previously defined query parameters, generates the *hash_query_real* (unique identifier of the filtered or queried real data in UUID format), and stores a copy of the filtered data in the MinIO server, together with the info file that

contains the metadata of the anonymized data request (ad_request_id, hash_query_real, timestamp and description).

3. The DP is notified that anonymized data is ready, and the processor is notified with the provision of an URL to download the anonymized data through the DP.

When the processor requesting the anonymized data uses the generated URL, the anonymized data is downloaded in the requested format (JSON or CSV) from the MinIO server of the RAI Node. In this step, the processor obtains a zip file with some files: the info file that contains metadata of the anonymized data (in JSON format) and one data file for each queried model_node that contains the requested anonymized data of each model node in the requested format.

4.2.3 Execute analysis locally and remotely

After requesting and obtaining SD or anonymized data for a data query of a RAI Node, processors can develop local algorithms using this data. Then, they can request the remote execution of those with the real data (HR and steps values) that reside inside the RAI Node. Figure 11 shows the workflow of this action for this prototype.

Figure 11: Prototype V1 workflow for executing analyses locally and remotely

When a controller uses the DP to request the remote execution of an experiment with the needed files and requirements for the analysis and the specified *hash_query_real* that identify the data to use for the analysis, the request is sent to the RAI Node. Once the RAI Node receives this request, the RAI Hub creates and saves in the MinIO server the necessary files and tools for the remote execution of the analysis and the experiment execution is scheduled and queued to the Remote Execution System. Then, this module runs the experiment with the real data inside the RAI Node, and when the results are ready, they are saved in the MinIO server, and the processor is notified through the DP.

After receiving this notification, the processor can request the analysis results through the DP. When the RAI Node receives this request, the RAI Hub finds these results in the MinIO server, and they are sent to the processor through the DP. This workflow can be repeated until the processor is happy with the results.

4.2.4 Register analysis results

The last workflow implemented in this prototype is the registration results. Once the processor that requested the remote execution of an analysis is happy with the obtained results, they can register them in the RAI Cloud server. The executed workflow in this action is depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Prototype V1 workflow for registering analyses results

4.2.5 Limitations

The limitations that have been identified from prototype V1 development are explained in this section.

Regarding the authentication method, the VITALISE service works with HTTP basic authentication and pre-shed user and password, and there is no shared authentication mechanism.

In the RAI Node, when new data is submitted, the metadata sent to the DP is computed for the whole collection of `model_node`s instead of being computed for each dataset. Furthermore, the person-related statistics are hardcoded when creating this metadata. The identified limitations regarding the SD and anonymized data workflows are listed next:

- The SD is only returned for the first `model_node` requested (unless a processor queries more than one `model_node`)
- There is no size limitation in the returned SD and anonymized data. All data points available for the query are provided.
- Even though the query results are the same for each SD or anonymized data request, a new copy of the real filtered data is stored in the MinIO server.
- The SDG model is trained for a complete `model_node`, which generates SD for all data points in the model node. SDG models are not trained specifically for each query.
- The used model for SDG is a tabular model provided by the SDV package (Patki, Wedge, and Veeramachaneni 2016) instead of being a more specific or personalized model for the HR and steps values, which can be treated as time series.

Besides, when requesting the remote execution of analysis with real data that resides in the RAI Nodes, the Remote Execution System is only compatible with analyses and scripts developed in the Python programming language.

4.3 Future prototypes

In prototypes V0 and V1 of the VITALISE service, the basic actions and workflows for controllers and processors have been implemented. This section presents the next actions and functionalities that are being implemented or are intended to be included in future prototypes.

The authorization and authentication methods for the modules of the VITALISE service will be improved with more robust and secure technologies, as introduced in section 3.6.

Moreover, more information about the available datasets in the RAI Nodes will be added. Firstly, the option for a processor to rate datasets will be added, and some visualization about the usage of

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each dataset (rate, interest, etc.) will be shown. Secondly, a more advanced data catalogue will be provided with advanced and improved data query parameters.

In the RAI Node of each LL, a GUI for controllers will be incorporated to make registering datasets and subjects and uploading data generated from the LL easier and more intuitive to them. A plugin service will be enabled to upload previously transformed data directly to the RAI Node for any model_node available in the Data Model. The scheduling of remote analysis execution will also be improved to provide a better and more robust task queueing, and support with other programming languages except for Python (R, C, MATLAB, JAVA, etc.) will be given.

Some improvements and future work will also be done regarding the SD and anonymized data workflows. First, the generation of SD will be done for different model_nodes and each specific query instead of generating SD for the complete collection of the model_node. Second, the size of returned SD and anonymized data to a processor will be limited due to memory issues. This process can be done by selecting the most representative data points to be returned when a processor requests SD or anonymized data. Third, some SD evaluation metrics will be provided with the SD to give the processors the option to analyse how representative the SD is regarding the real values and the quality of the SD. Finally, the option for processors to select the SDG model and perform a parameter selection will be integrated. This last functionality will imply the evaluation, selection, and design of more complex SDG models.

5 Conclusion

This document, which corresponds to D3.1 VITALISE Service Specification and is of report nature, describes the VITALISE service specification and architecture related to the VITALISE information and communication technologies (ICT) tools being developed in WP3.

This deliverable presents the requirements, the designed architecture and implemented solution for the VITALISE service. The main aim of this service is to manage the data on each Living Lab (LL) infrastructure and to share it based on the privacy, ethics and IPR legislation and policies established by each LL infrastructure. Four modules have been defined in the VITALISE service: the Data Model, the Discovery Portal, the RAI Node and the RAI Cloud Server.

The document starts by introducing the VITALISE service, a brief description of the modules that compose this service, the user stories and the technical requirements for the design and development of the VITALISE service (Section 2). Next, the overall architecture is depicted, and each of the four modules that compose the architecture are described from a technical and architectural perspective (Section 3). Finally, the technical development of the actual status of the service is updated, explaining the developed two prototypes (prototype V0 and prototype V1) and drawing the pending points and improvements for future prototype development (Section 4).

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